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CONCRETIZATION OF USER-REPRESENTATION MODELING USER (INTER)ACTION AS (COUNTER) PART OF A PRODUCT SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

In Human-centered design the whole system of (human) user and technical product is focused within the design process. Regarding the methodological support, current HCD-methodology supports primary phases of requirement definition and (usability) testing rather than the phase of designing as such. Within the conceptual design phase though, methodology from engineering and industrial design finds application for the development of interaction solution as well. However, this methodology focuses on designing technical product solutions and thus developing a product “around” the user. The user as such is seen as important part of the all-over system but not as partial solution of the whole user-product system. Within this paper an approach is depicted that focuses on the development of physical user (inter) action solutions as partial solutions of the all-over user-product system. By explicitly modeling these user (inter)actions this approach employs effects of externalization and confrontation by solution explication which are used in various conceptual design methods. Within a first design workshop the suggested approach is illustrated before experiences made are summarized and further research ideas are derived.

Keywords: Human-centered Design, Conceptual Design, User-Product Interaction

INTRODUCTION

Approaches for designing and developing products that rely on an intensive interaction between the user and the product - called interactive system in the following - are manifold. Within the fields of Human Factors Engineering, Industrial Design and Interface Design various Human-centered design

(HCD) approaches were developed. These approaches focus on the consideration of the user in its special physical and mental constitution and his needs within all different phases of a design process. Besides offering special sources for the design work as data compendiums, human factors design standards, principles and guidelines (Wickens et al., 2004) these approaches provide specific methods that support the operative fulfillment of the various development tasks in each phase. In regards to the different development phases it turns out that most of the available methodological support refers to the requirement definition as well as the testing and evaluation of generated solutions. Besides various open innovation approaches that foster the integration of user or customer (solution) ideas in the design process there is rather few methodological support for the solution finding process focusing on the special issues of interaction products. Thus the designer is left with standard solution finding methods known from disciplines as industrial and engineering design. As these methods focus on finding technical product solution and thus regard the (inter)action possibilities rather implicitly than as explicit partial solutions of the whole user-product system they aim for designing a product “around” the user. This seems inappropriate since the user and its (inter)action possibilities plays an important active role within the user-product system as pointed out by different approaches of Activity-centered design (ACD) (You & Deng, 2007). Having no methodological support focusing on the specific meaning of user-(inter) action within the conceptual design phase could result in missing possibly successful solutions as the following example of a student development project within an Industrial Design Engineering seminar shows.

Based on interdisciplinary development classes, where the students were taught in development methodology from the field of industrial design as well as engineering design (Schröer et al., 2010a) a team of students had to develop new solutions for the stowage of hand luggage within airliners. Their task consisted of accelerating the complete process from the passengers entering the plane over finding their seats and stowing their carry-on luggage up to taking seat at their places as this process was identified as reason for the (too) long and expensive dead time of the plane at ground before taking off. Within the tasks of problem identification and requirement definition the students used comprehensive user (behavior) observations, process imitation and process illustrations (Figure 1) to analyze why this process takes that long. Doing this, they realized that passengers standing in the aisle and stashing their hand-luggage in the overhead compartments (and keeping other passengers from moving) reasoned the time-consuming process of passengers entering the plane. In the conceptual design phase variation of the passenger's movement and standing positions while stashing their hand-luggage seemed to help developing solution for the given task. However, methodical approaches for the variation of this user (inter)action as solution could not be found which resulted in unsatisfying way of solving the task. Indeed the students developed, illustrated and combined new solutions; the new variants of underlying user-movements were anyways considered only implicitly and not modeled explicitly as solution. This eventually led to fixating on the first improvement of passenger "flows" as starting point for the further development of the interior instead of further explicating and varying the passenger movement as partial solution. As the example shows, existing design approaches of solution modeling and illustration do not meet the concerns that the user is incorporating an active role in the interaction with the product. Although the active role of the user is stressed in HCD but especially in Activity-centered design approaches (You & Deng, 2007) there is rather few methodological support that focuses of the employment of a user solution-contribution within. This paper tries to deliver an approach that should

help to consider this active role of the user within the conceptual design phase.

Figure 1. Illustration of analyzed passenger flow while entering the airliner cabin

BACKGROUND

This contribution focuses on the development of interaction solutions. As this issue is addressed excessively in human-centered design (HCD) existing methodical approaches suggested by literature of this field will be regarded in the following.

HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN

Systematic approaches for designing interactive systems are regarded by the field of Human-centered design. For the development process a standard procedural model for HCD is suggested within (DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010). This model illustrates the main phases of the HCD by four main phases. A particular attribute of this model is its iterative character that underlines the need for intensive evaluation of solutions during (especially the early) development process. The four recurring main phases of this process are:

- Understanding and determination of usage context
- Definition of user-requirements and organizational requirements

- Generation of design solutions
- Evaluation of design solutions by means of (user-) requirements

Figure 2. Main Human-centered design phases suggested by (DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010) .

According to this model activities and methods that support specific development tasks could be related to these four main phases. Based on a literature research relevant activities and methods have been collected and listed according to the four main phases in the following. As the focus of this paper lies on physical interaction approaches focusing physical user interactions and constitutions have mainly been taken into account.

Activities and methods for understanding and determination of usage context

As user characteristics, the task to accomplish and the organizational, technical and physical environment define the context in which the system will be used it is important to gather and analyze all kinds of information about this context (DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010). Subtasks supporting this analysis reach from user analysis over environment analysis to function and task analysis (Wickens et al., 2004). Gathering information for all these subtasks base on methods like observations, questionnaires and interviews. Supported by various guidelines provided by handbooks and compendiums (Wickens et al., 2004) different techniques could be employed to perform these tasks. Especially for the task and function analysis that plays an important role as it supports the understanding of the interaction

between user and product as such different modeling methods exist. Many of these modeling approaches stem originally from the field of software engineering and interface design and depict the interaction in its sequential procedure.

A first approach was established by Jacobson et al. in 1992 (Jacobson et al., 1992) for object-oriented software engineering. This bears on the modeling of *use cases* that describe actors trying to achieve a goal by using a (technical) system. Use cases are supposed to describe behavioral requirements and shift the attention away from the technical product descriptions back on the users. Use cases can be modeled using flow charts, sequence charts, Petri nets, or programming languages (Cockburn, 2007). Especially in form of prose text they can serve as means of communication among people from different disciplines and thus can stimulate discussions within a team about the product under development. Use Cases normally consist of different kinds of actors and stakeholders, preconditions, a scope that identifies the discussed system, a main success scenario and extensions that represent alternatives to the main success scenario (Cockburn, 2007). They can focus on modeling one user as well as more sequentially or parallel interacting users (Rumbaugh et al., 1991). More detailed and concretized use cases in form of *narrative scenarios* can furthermore be complemented by means of prototypical target group representatives - described in detail by *Personas* (Pruitt & Adlin, 2006) - to gather understanding about the user and its concrete interacting within the focused usage context (Wölfel & Bastian, 2010). Use Cases as well as narrative scenarios exist in different granularities/degrees of detail from *use case briefs* summarizing the use case over *casual use cases* consisting of a few paragraphs of text to *fully dressed use cases* featuring a long template with fields for stakeholders, minimum guarantees, post conditions, business rules, performance constraints, and so on (Cockburn, 2007). Furthermore he distinguishes the aims of use cases. Besides use cases that focus directly on the goals of the user he describes those that give an overview of the context and sequence of the existing user-goal centered use cases and those that illustrate the interaction on elementary sub-functions needed to achieve the user-goals. A more

abstract form of describing user interaction was suggested by Constantine in his approach of *Usage-centered Design* (Constantine, 1995). Within this approach he describes the interaction by means of actors as roles instead of personas fulfilling (very) elementary tasks in task cases. The aim of doing this is to avoid making unintended or premature assumptions about the concrete form of the product and its user interface to be designed (Constantine, 2006).

Activities and methods for definition of user-requirements and organizational requirements

The definition of user needs and requirements to the product or system is in most design projects a main task that builds upon the determination of the usage context. Most requirements can be derived from the analysis of the environment and the goals, needs and preferences of the focused user(s). The requirement definition concerning the physical constitution of the user can be supported by relevant findings in ergonomics documented in diverse *data compendiums* and *human factors standards*. While data compendiums comprise more elementary information concerning the physical constitution of the user or the user group human factors design standards are precise recommendations related to very specific areas or topics (Wickens et al., 2004). As the approach derived later in this paper focuses on physical interaction a short overview over existing compendiums is given in the following. Diverse data compendiums existing in form of *handbooks* (e.g. (Daams, 1994, DIN 33402-1, 2008) and *(web-based) databases* providing measurements and movement specific force exertions for the designer. Within these compendiums the various body measurements are listed differentiated by age, sex, region and further criteria. Developments of these measurements and body proportions over greater time frames as for example the increase of the average human all-over body size (DIN 33411-1, 1982) are furthermore recorded in time series to identify trends and could be used for dimensioning products. Information on the range of human motions in combination with the force evolution in different postures and over different motion courses are summarized in *task-non-specific norms* (DIN 33411-1, 1982) and *task-specific norms* (e.g. in

(Schaub et al., 2009) for human assembling activities). In regards to human factors design *standards* topic or area specific recommendations exist as for example in the different standards of ISO 9241. As mentioned above each of these standards focuses on supporting designing very specific elements as for example manual control elements by means of human force exertion (Daams, 1994) as well as by means of delay angles and areas of torque moments (DIN EN 894-3, 2010).

Based on these fundamental approaches more holistic *guideline* concepts like Usability or Controllability have been developed. Besides the physical constitution of the user these approaches take into account cognitive and mental aspects of the human being and translate them into requirements. Very general *principles* are given for example by Donald Norman focusing on the ease of use (Norman, 2002). Furthermore some of these guidelines provide a framework for testing products in form of giving criteria and suggesting testing designs as will be described later.

Activities and methods for generation of design solutions

According to ISO 9241-210 the generation of design solution for the interactive system is an innovation process that can be realized through a multitude of creative approaches to accomplish an appropriate user experience. This process comprises analysing the entire human-machine system to determine the best configuration of functions and features regarding the person-technology system as unit (Wickens et al., 2004). Here *scenario techniques* and various *sequential task modeling* and use case modeling approaches - described detailed above - can be applied to help defining functions and tasks to be accomplished by the user-product system. Within the following the allocation of functions to user and product has to be defined as well as the sequential order of interactions before the design process of the physical product as such starts by the identification of required interaction means and techniques through which the product will support the user (DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010, Wickens et al., 2004). Within this the allocation of functions constitutes a critical task. (Kirwan & Ainsworth, 1992) suggest an evaluation of the basic functions of

the human-machine system for the allocation. This could mean allocating in conjunction with a cost/benefit analysis to determine whether an allocation is feasible. Traditional views that allocate functions simply to the most capable part of the system are criticized as any psychological aspects are ignored. Various other approaches to accomplish this task could be found in literature e. g. (Price, 1990). However, this task still remains more art than science (Wickens et al., 2004).

The later design phases where the physical product as such has to be designed starts with developing first conceptual design solutions. These start out as relatively vague and become progressively more specific (Wickens et al., 2004). Over the whole design process the *building of prototypes* is recommended as methodical means. Especially simple and rough prototypes should be employed to allow the reflection of design solutions before refining and adapting of these embodied solutions can happen based on testing and evaluation (DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010). The employment of the former mentioned standards and guidelines is recommended over the whole design process, but especially during the early conceptual design phases. As soon as the conceptual design is established and the detailed design has to be defined the employment of visual models of the human user is suggested for simplifying the dimensioning process of interfaces within product design. First non-digital body templates are the *Kieler Manikin* (DIN 33408-1, 2008) or the SAE-Template while digital human-models like *Jack*, *Human Builder*, *RAMSIS*, *ANTHROPOS* and *NX Human* support the dimensioning process in a virtual development context combined with different kinds of CAD-tools (VDI 2209, 2009).

Activities and methods for evaluation of design solutions by means of (user-)requirements

The evaluation of design solutions is an important task for making sure that the developed product meets the requirements set up in the beginning (DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010). Thus the evaluation should happen by means of the requirement specifications supported by human factors standards and guidelines (Wickens et al., 2004). *Heuristic evaluation* is a systematic way of evaluating by analytically considering the characteristics of a product to

determine whether they meet human factors criteria. It should be conducted by experts and normally doesn't include the users of the system. Specific *standards* and *checklists* exist to support this task as for example Nielsen's *usability standards* (Nielsen, 1993), the *System Usability Scale (SUS)* (Brooke, 1996) or the *AttrakDiff*-questionnaire that also focuses on hedonic product qualities (Hassenzahl et al., 2003).

Besides heuristic approaches other types of evaluation can be differentiated according to the method of data collection which can base upon user *observation*, *interviews* and *questionnaires*. Furthermore physiological and physical measurements can be employed during user-product interaction for evaluation within *lab* and *field tests*. Here the very diverse methods that are employed in human factors research find application (Wickens et al., 2004). An overview over the wide field of testing and evaluation procedures is given by (Charlton & O'Brien, 2002). After having fully developed the product *final test* and *evaluation* have to be conducted. As these tests are concerned with any possible aspect of the system that affect human performance, safety, or the performance of the entire human-machine system this evaluation should involve "real" users.

CONCLUSION ON HCD METHODOLOGY

Summarizing the findings in literature concerning methods suggested supporting the human-centered design process the following conclusion can be drawn from the perspective of systematic product development:

Within the former sections activities of the four main tasks of the HCD process as well as the according methods suggested by literature were described. Based on the strong background of human factors research extensive methodical support exists for the phases of understanding and determination of the usage context as well as for the definition of (user-) requirements. Furthermore strong methodical support is provided for testing and evaluating developed system solutions on base of the former defined requirements.

Regarding the phase of generation of design solutions a gap concerning the methodological support could be identified from the perspective of systematic

product development which will be elaborated in the following.

To start the generation of solutions the configuration of functions regarding the person-technology system is suggested before defining the allocation of functions to user and product within the user-product system as well as the sequential order of interactions. For all these tasks various methodological approaches can be found. Regarding the following design process of the physical product as such the development of first relatively vague conceptual design solutions is recommended before concretizing them progressively to more specific ones. Besides suggesting the building of prototypes from a very early stage on and to employ these for an iterative evaluation (Wickens et al., 2004, DIN EN ISO 9241-210, 2010) no further methodological means is recommended. Thus, it can be stated that methodological support suggested by HCD literature for accomplishing the solution generation focuses mainly on the early design faces while approaches for operationally supporting the concrete solution finding process specifically for HCD are rare. In regards to the consideration of the user and its (inter)actions as partial solution within the user-product system only the relative abstract function allocation issue was addressed in literature. Regarding specifically the role of the user's concrete physical (inter)action possibilities and making them employable for the development of interaction solutions, no operational method could be found.

The generation of principle solution is an important activity not only in HCD but in product development and design in general. As the approaches suggested by these disciplines for this sub-phase - here called conceptual design - could be of interest for HCD as well they will be regarded in the following.

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

In systematic product development literature the design process is derived in several main phases. (Pahl et al., 2007) distinguish four phases (1) planning and task classification, (2) conceptual design, (3) embodiment design, and (4) detail design.

According to this classification the conceptual design phase comprises the development of principle

solutions on base of given requirements. Besides abstracting the problem this involves establishing function structures, searching and combining working principles to working structures and selecting a suitable working structure for firming it up into a principle solution (also called concept) (Pahl et al., 2007). The phase of establishing function structures focuses particularly on analyzing the system on an abstract level for identifying sub-functions (existing to meet the overall function). Building upon these functional structures the solution or 'synthesis' process starts by searching and developing conceptual solutions to solve the given design task. Results of this phase are further developed in the upcoming phases of embodiment and detail design where the product is developed into an ever more concrete form. In every of these phases various alternative solutions should be created to broaden the solution space (Roozenburg & Eekels, 1995) before selected solutions can be transferred into the next phase. To support the creation of solutions formal methods exist that support the generation of ideas for solutions. These methods will be illustrated in the following before their application in designing interactive products will be discussed.

Formal Idea generation Methods (IGM) and their application in conceptual design

As the name says these methods have been developed to support people in the generation of ideas and thus help broadening the solution space for a given problem, which is a main issue in different design phases. According to their cognitive mechanism or heuristic these idea generation methods can be classified into two groups (Schlicksupp, 2004). On the one hand there are *systematic-analytical methods* which support systematical problem decomposition and analysis and aim at increasing the comprehension of a system to enhance the quality of new ideas (Lindemann, 2007, Ulrich & Eppinger, 2004). On the other hand there are methods that focus on animating human's intuition by stimulating the unconscious thinking process of the human mind (Shah et al., 2001). Shah et al sub-classify the latter ones which are also called *creativity techniques* further into five categories: *germinal*, *transformational*, *progressive*, *organizational*, and *hybrid methods* (Shah et al.,

2000) as depicted in figure 3. An important issue in the application of these methods in regards to (conceptual) design activities is the explication of developed solutions in form of their concrete visualization and representation. On the one hand it supports the communication of ideas and thus allows idea generation in teams; on the other hand this explication is a sort of externalization of thoughts in the designer's head that helps to relieve his cognitive resources and allow him to reflect on his ideas by being confronted with them in a concrete representation. This effect of confrontation with first ideas explicated by different means (scribbles, sketches, rough physical models, etc.) could give inspiration and thus serve as "seeds" for the evolvement or the generation of new ideas for the designer, working in a team or alone (Sachse & Furtner, 2009). The issue of idea explication in form of different forms of representation is specifically addressed in some of the upper mentioned idea generation methods like different Brainwriting-techniques as *Method 635* (Rohrbach, 1969) and *C-Sketch* (Shah et al., 2001) as well as the further development of method 635 employing 3-dimensional solution representations (Schröer et al., 2010b). The employment of design catalogs that comprise existing solutions and solution principles supports this inspiring confrontation effect in a similar way by integrating external ideas in the idea generation process.

Explication of solution ideas in designing interactive systems: observations made in practice
 As there is no specific methodology supporting the

conceptual design of interaction solutions the application of general conceptual design methods happens in practice quite often. However, in regards to the explication of solution ideas in form of concrete sketches as they find application within most conceptual design processes one important observation could be made within several interdisciplinary student development projects. Although most of the interaction solution ideas developed in these projects were developed in terms of a complete solution comprising the human (inter)action solution and the product solution most of the explications only illustrated the product-side part. The partial solution contributed by the human user in its physical constitution was considered implicitly but was barely explicated in the illustrations.

CONCEPTUAL HCD: EMPLOYING IGM-EFFECTS FOR HCD

There are three major findings that motivated the approach developed in the following. **First**, no specific methods for supporting the conceptual design phase in human-centered design by taking into account characteristic issues of interaction solutions could be identified in literature. Especially in regards to the important role the user's physical (inter)action can take (You & Deng, 2007) - representing a partial solution within the all-over user-product system - no methodological approach could be found. **Second**, excessive general methodological support for conceptual design is provided by literature in the field of engineering and industrial design. Within

Figure 3. Classification of idea generation methods [shah et al. 2001]

this, the special issue of explication of generated solutions by means of different representations is addressed by several methods to improve the solution finding process.

Third, general conceptual design methods brought up by different disciplines find application in the development of interaction solutions. Within this the human being is considered as active part of the user-product system. However, although the user's (inter)action possibilities could be interpreted as partial solutions to the all-over system they are not treated in a similar way as product solutions if it comes to explication and visualization.

Based on these findings the question arose in how far the effect of externalization employed by various IGM could be applied for the development of interaction solutions, especially of user (inter)action solutions. If an explicit visualization of the human user, its physical characteristics, and its (inter)action possibilities could serve as inspiration for designing interaction solutions it might serve as catalysts for the development of new solution ideas on the product side as well.

Starting a solution generation process by exclusively searching and illustrating (inter)action possibilities for a desired interaction before developing solutions on the product solution side could be an alternative approach, promising to enlarge the all-over solution space. This approach was applied in a first workshop as will be described in the following.

IDEA GENERATION WORKSHOP ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF USER (INTER)ACTION SOLUTIONS EMPLOYING EFFECTS OF IGM

The basic idea of the workshop was to follow the former mentioned suggestion to start the conceptual design phase of an interactive system by collecting; developing and illustrating possible user (inter)action solutions as partial solutions before developing appropriate technical product solutions.

Development task

Within this workshop the approach was applied to the development of sports equipment, in detail to the development of a line-management system for kite surfing. The actual development task was: *Finding find solutions that allow varying the lengths of the kite lines while riding to allow launching and*

landing the kite with short lines at spots were there's too less space to wind up the complete line length but still allow riding with long lines when having left the starting spot. The existing kite shouldn't be varied in its general character as well as the steering of the kite by a bar attached to a harness should remain unchanged.

Participants and procedure

The task had to be executed by a team of three doctoral students of the field of engineering design that were guided within their work by the author. To find a solution the participants were asked to develop ideas by regarding the user in its physical representation - including force and moment production as well as "all" possible human movements. All illustrations should thus depict (almost) exclusively the user in its certain (inter)action and rather no product solution component. In regards to the procedure the participants were asked to illustrate their ideas in form of scribbles and sketches (completed by describing text elements) on paper and a whiteboard and explaining them in an oral discussion which represents a combination of *brainstorming*, *brainwriting*, and *gallery method*. These techniques were chosen as they are commonly applied in conceptual design practice in engineering and industrial design because of their ease of application without having great experience using creativity methods and their strong support of team creativity. Besides completing the task the doctoral students were asked to reflect on their doing and speak out loud issues they had with the suggested approach.

Observations and results

After a short period of explaining and discussing the suggested approach the participants started to develop and illustrate their ideas. To do so they generally started by illustrating their ideas in a pantomime-like way using their own body to reflect and communicate. At the same time the participants searched for verbal explications (e.g. hula-hoop movement or knee-bend movement) for their solutions to support the communication. After the initial illustration by means of their own bodies they started capturing their ideas by simple sketches. Within this, all movements were illustrated by means

of arrows while the movement solutions as such were mainly illustrated without any specific technical product as it was asked from the very beginning. All participants agreed arbitrarily on abstracting the task to “bring in the lines” while two participants suggested to fractionize the given task in the beginning to “bringing human into contact with lines” and “give movement by the human”. In the following most of the found solutions focused the latter subtask although the solutions sometimes implicitly aimed for accomplishing both tasks. As soon as first solutions of partial systems were presented by means of different limbs their movement was varied (e.g. pulling with arm, rotating arm). Sometimes identified movements of one body part were transferred to other ones (e.g. full body hula-hoop movement → hand hula-hoop movement; rotation of arms → rotation of whole body).

Participant feedback and discussion of observations

Observations and direct participant feedback after the workshop showed that the participants didn't feel comfortable and didn't know how to cope with the new approach in the beginning. It was perceived as unclear, what they were allowed to do and what not. After first solutions had been developed and illustrated the participants lost that feeling of uncertainty and began to enjoy the approach. Especially the pantomime-like communication of ideas was perceived as motivating. In the following first visualized ideas were picked-up for evolution. At this, effects like *variation* of movement parameters as well as *analogy transfer* could be identified. These observations seem to confirm that the desired externalization effect can be triggered by the approach. However, several questions came up during this first small tentative workshop which will be addressed in the following conclusion

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Based on experiences made in university design projects and findings in literature reviewed in the fields of human-centered design, engineering and industrial design an approach for developing interaction solutions was derived in this paper. This approach combines the effects of solution

explication with the idea of employing the physical human (inter)action possibilities as partial solutions of the user-product system within the conceptual design process. This approach was applied to a first tentative workshop within a development project of sports equipment.

In regards to employing the explication effect for developing interaction solutions this application could be seen as successful. However, several questions arose of the application of the approach. One was the issue of how technical product solutions could be developed on base of these human (inter)action solutions and in how far the latter ones are of advantage to this. Within the workshop it could be observed that participants developed already product solutions compatible to the first (inter)action solutions but didn't explicate them. This leads to the assumption that developing product partial solutions can be developed on the base of pure human (inter)action solutions. Building up chains where the development of user (inter) interaction solutions could trigger product component solutions and where these product component solutions could again trigger the development of user (inter)action solutions could be an evolution of the approach which should be examined in future workshops. Another question arose of the explication methods suggested and employed within the workshop. Although sketches were used successfully the employment of verbal descriptions, but particularly of pantomime and gestures implies the question after the right tools and media to externalize the user (inter) action solutions. Especially alternative media as video recordings and means as simple and rough prototypes seem to represent alternative representation forms which could enhance the externalization and inspiration effect. The employment of those representation media should thus be considered in further examinations as well.

Besides these two rather concrete questions further questions regarding the applicability to different kinds of interactive products, the influence of varying (explication) skills brought by different development disciplines should be regarded in future work as well as the general question in how far the solutions delivered by this approach would not have

emerge without coming explicitly and exclusively from the user and its (inter)action possibilities.

OUTLOOK

Besides answering the questions posed in the former conclusion to evaluate the power of the suggested approach further ideas of employing the general approach in a more operative way have been developed.

If (inter) action solutions can be explicated in the same way as product partial solutions are illustrated, one could try to employ “classical” conceptual design methods for (re)combination - e. g. the morphological box - to combine different user (inter)action solutions with others but as well with product component solutions. Furthermore the inspiring effect of the confrontation with developed ideas could be fostered by building catalogs of user (inter) actions similar to catalogs of principle solutions as they exist in engineering design. Thus, the variety of potentially “useful” human (inter)actions could be made available to the designer during the idea generation. Listings of human body movements as they exist in ergonomics, sport science but as well in form of gestures in the field of interaction design could be employed for this matter. Last but not least; general engineering design principles like abstraction, fractionalization and variation could be employed to human (inter)action solution as well. In how far this could help improving solution finding process for interaction solutions is another open question that could be addressed in future research.

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